

TECHNOLOGIES FOR DEVELOPING LIBRARY CULTURE IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: This thesis analyzes the current issues of forming and developing a reading culture in students in the modern educational process. The culture of reading is considered not only as a means of acquiring knowledge, but also as a means of developing personal development, critical thinking, aesthetic taste and speech culture. The author highlights the role of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, information and communication tools in the development of a reading culture, as well as approaches appropriate to the age and psychological characteristics of students.

Keywords: reading culture, educational technologies, independent reading, interactive approach, aesthetic education, creative thinking.

Introduction.

One of the main goals of the modern education system is the comprehensive development of the individual, the formation of independent thinking, analytical approach, aesthetic taste and spiritual values. The culture of reading plays an important role in this process. Reading is not only a reading skill, but also a socio-cultural process that develops cognitive, affective and metacognitive competencies. In the formation of these competencies, especially in the younger generation, the integration of educational institutions, the pedagogical process and modern technologies is of crucial importance. In today's digital information space, the formation of students' thinking, cultural views and interest in books is becoming increasingly complex. Therefore, the development of a reading culture through innovative pedagogical technologies in education, in particular, information and communication technologies (ICT), a person-centered approach, teaching based on media literacy, contextual learning, and reading based on collective discussion, has become an urgent issue. Research shows that students with high reading activity are distinguished not only by their level of knowledge, but also by their social adaptability, communication culture and the ability to think creatively. Therefore, the development of pedagogical strategies aimed at developing this culture in students and their integration into educational practice is one of the priority areas of modern pedagogy.

Methodology:

The issue of forming a reading culture in students is a multifaceted problem that requires not only pedagogical, but also sociocultural and psychological approaches. In the research conducted in this area, I chose integrated, systematic, person-oriented and activity-based concepts as a methodological approach. Because it is through these approaches that it is possible to fully understand the personality of the student, select and implement technologies that meet their needs.

During the research, an empirical approach based on various pedagogical experiences and observations on the activation of reading played an important role. The attitude, choice, interest, and analytical skills of students in the classroom and extracurricular activities were studied. In this regard, diagnostic tests, questionnaires, interviews, and pedagogical observation methods became the main research tools.

In addition, in order to study the issue of reading culture in more depth, an attempt was made to assess the elements of qualitative research - that is, to analyze the thoughts, emotional state, and attitude of students to the works they read, to enter their inner world, and to express themselves. In this process, many aspects were clarified by analyzing student activities based on a reflective approach and organizing discussions among them.

From a methodological point of view, it was emphasized that the culture of reading is not limited to acquiring knowledge, but is closely related to the development of moral-aesthetic, cultural, communicative competencies. Therefore, it was determined that each technology, method and tool should be aimed not only at knowledge, but also at educating and forming a socially active personality. Thus, the methodological foundations used in this study made it possible to identify effective technologies that serve to instill a positive attitude towards books in students, to educate them as active, conscious, independent readers.

Discussion:

The weakening of the culture of reading in modern society is considered a global problem. Especially among the younger generation, the rapid flow of information, social networks, video content are displacing the habit of reading books. In such conditions, it is not easy to develop in students such aspects as deep thinking, text analysis, perception of images, and the formation of aesthetic taste. Therefore, the pedagogical technologies put forward in this article are not just a set of methods, but complex, but necessary tools aimed at shaping the personality of the reader through books.

One of the important conclusions identified during the study is that the reading culture does not form by itself, but is the result of constant, systematic and purposeful influences. If the teacher himself is not a book lover, this culture will not form in the reader. Therefore, the role of the pedagogical person in this process should be emphasized. The teacher should not only be a giver of knowledge, but also a person who instills love for books, inspires, and turns the process of reading into a pleasant experience.

The effectiveness of interactive methods in encouraging reading was also determined, including such methods as “circle of ideas”, “creative questions”, “literary debates”, “book presentations”, “virtual libraries”. Through these technologies, students not only read, but also analyze what they have read, discuss, argue, and finally, form their personal worldview through books.

Another aspect that is worth noting in the discussion process is the attitude of the family, environment, and peer group to reading, which also directly affects the student's reading. If a child feels a reading environment at home, at school, and in the community, then this habit is formed as a social norm. Otherwise, he perceives reading as an obligation, not as a pleasure.

So, the culture of reading is not an individual, but a socio-cultural phenomenon. In order to develop it, a cultural support system must be formed not only in the classroom, but also in the general environment of the educational institution, in the family, and even in society. In this regard, modernization of school libraries, targeted use of digital resources, and support for students' initiatives related to books are important factors. Thus, technologies for developing a reading culture are a pedagogical strategy that requires a multi-stage, complex and sustainable approach. It not only increases the quality of education, but also enriches the student's personality spiritually and morally, preparing him for social life.

Conclusion:

In today's globalization and digital society, the ability to read a book, understand it and extract vital meaning from it is becoming one of the most important competencies of a student's personality. And the reading culture is a solid foundation of this skill. During the study, it was realized that the formation of this culture is not limited to the teacher's assignment or any activity in the lesson schedule. This is the result of a conscious, continuous, meaningful educational and educational process.

By developing and implementing technologies aimed at developing reading, the level of thinking, social position, spiritual world and aesthetic taste of the

student will change significantly. In particular, interactive approaches, person-oriented methods, digital technologies and creative tasks encourage the student to be active, allowing him not only to read the text, but also to understand it, analyze it and draw life lessons. Most importantly, through the culture of reading, the student forms his personal values, moral criteria, patriotic and humanistic views. This process should be recognized not as the only result of education, but as the most important stage of personal development. In conclusion, the development of a reading culture in students is one of the priority areas of modern pedagogy. This requires every teacher to think in a new way, master modern technologies, and most importantly, to instill a love for books. Because love for books is not just an incentive to read, but also an illumination of the human soul, enrichment of its inner world and change of attitude to life.

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